

Scurvy on Jacques Cartier's second voyage to North America (Winter 1535-1536)

A large proportion of the crew died from scurvy on Cartier's second voyage to Newfoundland. This epidemic is one of the earliest unambiguous historical descriptions of scurvy. This document contains two separate translations of the epidemic to English. The texts are made available in Zenodo so that the story is easier to reach and easier to read, and links to the digitized versions of the books are also available.

An earlier unambiguous description of scurvy was described by Joinville (1249):
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17341537>

Biographies about Jacques Cartier:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jacques_Cartier
<https://www.britannica.com/biography/Jacques-Cartier>
<https://www.biography.com/history-culture/jacques-cartier>
<https://thecanadianencyclopedia.ca/en/article/jacques-cartier>
<https://exploration.marinersmuseum.org/subject/jacques-cartier/>
https://www.biographi.ca/en/bio/cartier_jacques_1491_1557_1E.html
<https://www.heritage-history.com/index.php?c=resources&s=char-dir&f=cartier>
<https://www.historymuseum.ca/virtual-museum-of-new-france/the-explorers/jacques-cartier-1534-1542/>
<https://www.oxfordbibliographies.com/display/document/obo-9780199730414/obo-9780199730414-0252.xml>

In addition to the two translation, a third annotated version was also found, by **H. P. Biggar** (1924):
https://archive.org/details/voyagesofjacques0000cart_f4g3/page/n9/mode/2up
<https://archive.org/details/voyagesofjacques0000hpbi/page/n7/mode/2up>
https://archive.org/details/voyagesofjacques0000cart_f4g3/page/82/mode/2up Start of the second voyage.

On page 204, the following describes the start of the scurvy epidemic, with the French text in parallel:
"OF A GREAT SICKNESS AND PESTILENCE WHICH VISITED THE PEOPLE OF STADACONA, BY WHICH, FOR HAVING FREQUENTED THEM, WE WERE ATTACKED TO SUCH AN EXTENT THAT THERE DIED AS MANY AS TWENTY-FIVE OF OUR MEN."
https://archive.org/details/voyagesofjacques0000cart_f4g3/page/204/mode/2up

Yellow is used to indicate more important sections such as the symptoms of scurvy. This text is available at:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17348075>
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<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/?term=hemila+h>
<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

Spruce and fir as antiscorbutic was discussed by Lind:

James Lind: Treatise on Scurvy (1772) 3rd ed p.177-180

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/176/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/176/mode/2up>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt/items?canvas=199>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=ucm.5320216006&seq=201>

p.177

But it appears by the experience of the northern *American* colonies, as also of several other countries, that **spruce** beer is not only an effectual preservative against it, but an excellent remedy.

The antiscorbutic virtue of the **fir** was, like many other of our best medicines, accidentally discovered in *Europe*. When

p.178

the *Swedes* carried on a war against the *Muscovites*, almost all the soldiers of their army were destroyed by the scurvy, having putrid gums, rigid tendons, &c. But a stop was put to the progress of this disease, by the advice of *Erbenius* the King's physician, with a simple decoction of fir-tops; by which the most deplorable cases were perfectly recovered, and the rest of the soldiers prevented from falling into it. It also proved an excellent gargle for the putrid gums. From thence this medicine came into great reputation, and the common fir, *picea major*, or *abies rubra*, was afterwards called *pinus antiscorbutica*. *Pinus sylvestris*, the mountain-pine, has likewise been found to be possessed of very great antiscorbutic virtues, of which a late accident has furnished a convincing proof. In the year 1736 two squadrons of ships fitted out by the court of *Russia*, for the discovery of a north east passage to *China*, were obliged to winter in *Siberia*. One of them commanded by *Demetrius Laptiew*, not far from the mouth of the river *Lena*, was attacked by the scurvy. The men in their distress by chance found near them this tree growing in the mountains, and experienced it to have a most surprising antiscorbutic virtue. At the same time while *Alexius Tschirikow* was passing the winter in the river *Sudoma*, a considerable number of his men were also

p.179

dreadfully afflicted with this disease. After various fruitless attempts to discover a remedy able to put a stop to this cruel disaster, he at length accidentally had recourse likewise to the pines which grew plentifully on the mountains, by which all his men were recovered in a few days. In some the medicine proved gently laxative, in others it affected the body so mildly, that its operation was scarce sensible.

I am inclined to believe, from the description given by **Cartier** of the *ameda* tree, with a decoction of the bark and leaves of which his men were so speedily recovered, that it was the large swampy *American* spruce tree. The shrub spruce, of that sort vulgarly called the *black*, which makes the most wholesome beer, affords a balsam superior to most turpentine, though known only to a few physicians.

A simple decoction of the tops, cones, leaves, or even green bark and wood of these trees, is an excellent antiscorbutic medicine: but it will I am apt to think become much more so when fermented, as in making spruce beer. By carrying a few bags of spruce or its extract to sea, this wholesome

p.180

drink may be prepared at any time. But where it cannot be had, the common fir-tops used for fuel in the ship, should be first boiled in water, and the decoction afterwards fermented with *molasses*, in the common method of making spruce beer; to which a small quantity of wormwood and horse-raddish root (which it is easy to preserve fresh at sea) may be added. The juice of the cocoa nut-tree was experienced to be of very great benefit to several persons afflicted with the scurvy, on board the *Dolphin* and *Tamer* ships of war, in their late voyage round the world. By an Admiralty order a trial was made in those ships of malt made into wort, which was given to several patients in the scurvy, without producing any very considerable effect.

Fir was mentioned by Nitzsch for treating scurvy:

Description of scurvy in the Russian Army by Nitzsch (1747)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17296087>

Horse-raddish and **fir-tops** steeped and fermented with beer; or infused in brandy; and mustard, where no fever or other symptoms forbid their use, are extremely serviceable, principally in the petechial and pale mucous scurvies, after cleansing the stomach and intestines.

More recent discussions of vitamin C content in fir and spruce trees:

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2647905>

<https://doi.org/10.1186/1746-4269-5-5>

<https://doi.org/10.3138/cbmh.7.2.161>

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamadermatol.2014.4582>

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.99.2563.125.a>

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.98.2545.325.a>

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.98.2541.242.a>

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.98.2541.241>

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.98.2536.132.a>

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.97.2520.354.c>

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.92.2376.35.b>

A memoir of Jacques Cartier, his voyages to the St. Lawrence

A memoir of Jacques Cartier, sieur de Limoilou, his voyages to the St. Lawrence, a bibliography and a facsimile of the manuscript of 1534 by **Baxter**, James Phinney, 1831-1921

This book has been extensively digitized, at least 20 versions, indicating lack of coordination between libraries:

<https://archive.org/details/amemoirjacquesc00alfogoog/page/n17/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/amemoirjacquesc00robegoog/page/n11/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/amemoirofjacquescartierjamesphinneybaxter1906/page/n7/mode/2up>
https://archive.org/details/bub_gb_Grx1AAAAMAAJ/page/n5/mode/2up
<https://archive.org/details/cu31924028727893/page/n13/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/memoirofjacquesc00baxt/page/n11/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/memoirofjacquesc00cart/page/n9/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/memoirofjacquesc01baxt/page/n11/mode/2up>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=coo1.ark:/13960/t6d22h85t&seq=15>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=hvd.32044021007208&seq=21>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=hvd.32044105369003&seq=15>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=hvd.tz124y&seq=15>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=loc.ark:/13960/t1cj8rp03&seq=13>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=mdp.39015005659050&seq=13>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=nyp.33433067355861&seq=13>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=nyp.33433067355879&seq=15>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uiuo.ark:/13960/t6930zf2n&seq=13>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=yale.39002034527680&seq=13>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=yale.39002040580228&seq=11>

https://books.google.com/books/about/A_Memoir_of_Jacques_Cartier_Sieur_de_Lim.html?id=xyz4BhtSeUoC

Scurvy on Jacques Cartier's second voyage to North America (winter 1535-1536)

Description of the epidemic of scurvy by **Baxter**,¹ 1831-1921

The text is from:

<https://archive.org/details/memoirofjacquesc00baxt/page/190/mode/2up> p.190

<https://archive.org/details/memoirofjacquesc00cart/page/190/mode/2up> p.190

<https://archive.org/details/amemoirofjacquescartierjamesphinneybaxter1906/page/n215/mode/2up> p.190

https://archive.org/details/bub_gb_Grx1AAAAMAAJ/page/n205/mode/2up p.190

<https://archive.org/details/cu31924028727893/page/190/mode/2up> p.190

<https://archive.org/details/amemoirjacquesc00robegoog/page/190/mode/2up> p.190

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=yale.39002034527680&seq=216>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=nyp.33433067355861&seq=232>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=mdp.39015005659050&seq=220>

A MEMOIR OF JACQUES CARTIER

SIEUR DE LIMOILOU

HIS VOYAGES TO THE ST. LAWRENCE

A BIBLIOGRAPHY AND A FACSIMILE OF
THE MANUSCRIPT OF 1534
WITH ANNOTATIONS,
ETC.

BY

JAMES PHINNEY BAXTER, A. M., Litt. D.

NEW YORK

DODD, MEAD & COMPANY

1906

1 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/James_Phinney_Baxter
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uc1.b2844243&seq=7>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=hvd.32044086338092&seq=6>
<https://archive.org/details/memoirofjacquesc00baxt/page/n17/mode/2up>

OF A GREAT SICKNESS AND DEATH WHICH CAME TO THE PEOPLE OF STADACONÉ, FROM WHICH, FOR HAVING CONSORTED WITH THEM, WE HAVE BEEN CARRIED OFF BY IT, INSOMUCH THAT THERE ARE DEAD OF OUR MEN EVEN TO THE NUMBER OF TWENTY-FIVE

p.190

In the month of December we were advised that the mortality had fallen upon the people of Stadaconé² to such a degree that there were dead more than fifty of them by their own confession. On account of which we forbade them our fort³ and from coming about us; but, notwithstanding having driven them away, the sickness began among us in a marvelous and most unknown manner, for some lost substance, and their legs became large and swollen, and their sinews shrank and grew black as coal, and with some all besprinkled with spots of blood almost purple. Then the said sickness mounted to the hips, thighs, and shoulders, to the arms and to the neck, and the mouth withal⁴ became so infected and the gums so putrid that all the flesh fell away from them, even to the roots of the teeth, which almost all fell out.⁵ And to such a degree did the said sickness spread in our three ships that, by the middle of February, of a hundred and ten men that we were, there were not ten sound, so that one could not help the other, which was a thing piteous to behold, considering the place where we were; for the folks of the country came every day before our fort, who saw but few people up, and already there were eight dead there and more than fifty in whom one could not expect more life.

p.191

Our captain, seeing the misery and sickness so active, had everybody put to prayers and supplications, and had an image in remembrance of the Virgin

2 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stadacona> Stadacona, a 16th-century Iroquoian village near Quebec City.

3 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fort_\(disambiguation\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fort_(disambiguation))

4 Withal. In addition.

5 There can be no doubt as to the nature of this disease, as Cartier accurately describes the scurvy (*scorbuticus*), then but little understood. Lescarbot says that the disease was known to Hippocrates, and cites the description of Olaus Magnus, who denominates it *sorbet*—literally, bad habit; an apt title, since it is caused by careless exposure to cold, dampness, and impure air and water, as well as by long-continued use of salt food.

Vide Histoire de la Nouvelle France, Lescarbot, tome ii, p. 453.

Description of Scurvy Symptoms by Olaus Magnus (1555):

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13380745>

Mary placed against a tree about a bow-shot distant from our fort across the snow and ice, and ordered that the Sunday ensuing they should say mass at the said place, and that all those who could walk, the sound as well as the sick, should go in procession, singing the seven psalms of David, with the Litany, while praying the said Virgin that it might please her to pray her dear Child that he would have pity upon us. The said mass having been said and chanted before the said image, the captain bound himself a pilgrim to Our Lady who causes herself to be prayed to at Roquemado,⁶ promising to go thither if God should give him grace to return into France. This day Philippe Rougemont, native of Amboise, passed away,⁷ at the age of about twenty years.

p.192

And because the sickness was unknown, the captain had the body opened to see if one might get some knowledge from it to preserve, if it were possible, the rest. And it was found that the heart was white and withered, surrounded with more than a pot of water red as a date; the liver fair, but the lungs wholly black and mortified; and all his blood was shrunken above his heart; for when he was opened there issued from above the heart a great abundance of infected blood. Likewise the spleen toward the spine was about two fingers' breadth a little broached as if it had been rubbed on a rough stone. After this was seen he was opened and one thigh cut into, the which was very black outside, but within the flesh was found fair enough. This done, he was buried as well as one could. May God by his holy grace forgive his soul and all trespasses ! Amen.

And from day to day the said sickness continued in such manner that many a time it was so that in all the three ships there were not three sound men, so that in one of the said ships there was not a man who was able to go below deck to draw water any more for himself than for the others; and presently there were already many of them dead, whom it behooved us, through weakness, to put under the snow, for it was not possible for us to open the earth for them, which was frozen, we were so feeble and had so little

p.193

6 Roquemado. Lescarbot says Roquemadou, and explains, "pour mieux dire à Roque amadou c'est à dire des amans. C'est vn bourg en Querci, ou il y va force pelerins." It is the modern Rocamadour in the department of Lot, and is a market-town of about fifteen hundred inhabitants.

7 "Trespasa" is the word used by Cartier.

strength. And so were we in a marvelous fear of the people of the country, that they might perceive our misery and weakness; and in order to cover up the said sickness, when they came near our fort, our captain, whom God has always preserved, would come forth straight **before them with two or three men, both sound and sick, whom he had come out after him**, and when he saw them outside the palisade he made a pretense of wishing to beat them, crying and throwing sticks after them, sending them aboard, showing by signs to the said savages that he made all his folks work in the ships, some to calk,⁸ others to make bread and do other work, and that it was not good that they should come to idle outside, which they believed. And the said captain made the said sick men beat and make a noise within the ships with sticks and stones, feigning to calk. And at the time **we were so smitten with the said sickness that we had almost lost hope of ever returning into France**, if God by his infinite goodness and mercy had not looked upon us in pity and given knowledge of a remedy against all sicknesses, the most excellent that was ever seen or found upon the earth, as mention shall be made in this chapter.

THE NUMBER OF DAYS THAT WE WERE IN THE HARBOR OF ST. CROIX AND FROZEN IN THE ICE AND SNOW, AND THE NUMBER OF THE MEN DECEASED AFTER THE BEGINNING OF THE SICKNESS UNTIL THE MIDDLE OF MARCH

From the middle of November until the fifteenth day of April we were continually locked up in the ice, the which was more than two fathoms⁹ in thickness, and over the land there was the height of four feet of snow and more, so that it was higher than the sides of our ships, the which lasted until the said time, insomuch that our drinkables were all frozen within the casks. And throughout our said ships, as well as above, the ice upon the sides was four inches in thickness, and all the said river was frozen, inasmuch as the fresh water continued as far as above Hochelaga,¹⁰ at which time **there deceased among us even to the number of twenty-five persons of the**

p.194

8 Calk. To seal (a gap or seam) with a waterproof filler or sealant.

9 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fathom> Two fathoms is not consistent with 4 inches.

10 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hochelaga_\(village\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hochelaga_(village)) Hochelaga is now Montreal.

chiefest and best companions that we had, who died by the aforesaid sickness. And for a while there were more than fifty of them in whom one could not expect more life, and all the rest sick, so that not any of them were exempt except three or four. But God, by his holy grace, regarded us in pity, and sent us the knowledge and the remedy for our cure and health in the sort and manner which shall be related in this chapter.

HOW BY THE GRACE OF GOD WE HAD KNOWLEDGE OF THE KIND OF A TREE BY THE WHICH ALL THE SICK WERE CURED AND RECOVERED HEALTH AFTER HAVING USED OF IT, AND THE MANNER OF USING IT

One day our captain, seeing the sickness so violent and his people so smitten with it, being gone outside of the fort and walking by himself upon the ice, beheld a band of folks coming from Stadaconé, in the which was Dom Agaya, whom the captain had seen, only ten or twelve days before, very sick with the sickness which his people had; for he had one of his legs as big at the knee as a child of two years, and all the sinews¹¹ of it shrunken, his teeth lost and spoiled, and his gums putrid and corrupted.

p.195

The captain, seeing the said Dom Agaya sound and well, was glad, hoping to know from him how he was cured, so as to give aid and succor to his men. When they were arrived near the fort, the captain asked him how he was cured of his sickness; the which Dom Agaya responded that he was cured by the juice and refuse of the leaves of a tree, and that it was the only remedy for the sickness. The said captain asked him if there was not some of it thereabouts, and if he would show him some of it in order to cure his servant, who had taken the said sickness in the said Canada while he abode with Donnacona¹²—not wanting to declare to him the number of the crew who were sick. Then the said Dom Agaya sent two women with the captain to fetch some of it, who brought nine or ten branches of it, and showed us how one should strip the bark and the leaves from the said tree and put the whole to boil in water, then

11 Sinew. Tendon, ligament.

12 The chief of the St. Lawrence Iroquois village of Stadacona, located at the present site of Quebec City.
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Donnacona>

to drink of it every other day and put the refuse on the swollen and diseased legs, and that the said tree would cure all the sick. They call the said tree in their tongue *amedda*.¹³

Soon after the captain had some of the beverage made in order to have the sick drink of it, of whom there were none of them who might wish to try the said beverage except one or two who put themselves to the venture of trying it. Shortly after they had drunken of it they received benefit, which was found to be a real and evident miracle; for all the sick, of whatever they were infected, after having drunken of it two or three times, recovered health and vigor, so that such as there were of the said crew who had the syphilis five or six years previous to the said sickness were by this medicine completely cured. After this was seen and understood there was such strife for the said medicine that they would have killed themselves to see who first should have it; so that a tree as big and as tall as any tree I ever saw was used up in less than eight days, which had such effect that if all the doctors of Lorraine and Montpellier had been there, with all the drugs of Alexandria, they could not have done so much in a year as the said tree did in six days; for it profited us so much that all those who would use it recovered health and soundness, thanks to God.

p.196

13 *Amedda*. Lescarbot says “annedda,” and Hakluyt “amedda” and “hanneda.” Some writers suppose this to have been the white spruce (*Picea alba*), and others the white pine (*Pinus strobus*); but the *P. alba* is a better anti-scorbutic. Cartier’s relation of the rapid recovery of his men overstrains our credulity, and, as though he foresaw this, he throws in the convenient suggestion, with which Pope sympathizes, that it was a veritable miracle. Cf. Jacques Cartier, Pope, p. 876; Histoire de la Nouvelle France, Lescarbot, tome ii, p. 451 *et seq.*
Pope: Jacques Cartier:
<https://archive.org/details/jacquescartierhi00popeuoft/page/8/mode/2up>
https://archive.org/details/cihm_12076/page/n11/mode/2up
Lescarbot: Histoire de la Nouvelle-France
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/22268> [in French]]
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/21199>
https://archive.org/details/historyofnewfran07lesc_0/page/8/mode/2up Vol II, Book III, Chapter XXIV, p.149-154.

Scurvy on Jacques Cartier's second voyage to North America (winter 1535-1536)

Vol II, Chapter XXIV p.149-154.

Description of the epidemic of scurvy by **Lescarbot**¹⁴ 1570?-1630?

The text is from:

https://archive.org/details/historyofnewfran07lesc_0/page/148/mode/2up

<https://archive.org/details/historyofnewfran07lesc/page/148/mode/2up>

https://archive.org/details/cihm_72114/page/n163/mode/2up

In French:

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/22268>

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/21199>

THE HISTORY OF NEW FRANCE

BY

MARC LESCARBOT

WITH AN ENGLISH TRANSLATION, NOTES
AND APPENDICES BY

W. L. GRANT, M.A. (Oxon.)

AND AN INTRODUCTION BY

H. P. BIGGAR, B. Litt. (Oxon.)

IN THREE VOLUMES

VOLUME II

TORONTO

THE CHAMPLAIN SOCIETY

1911

¹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Marc_Lescarbot
<https://archive.org/details/historyofnewfran01lesc/page/n11/mode/2up>
https://www.biographi.ca/en/bio/lescarbot_marc_1E.html

IN the month of December we were advised that pesti- p.149
lence was rife among the people of Stadaconé,¹⁵ in so
much that by their own confession there were already
more than fifty dead; for which reason we forbade them to
visit our fort or our vicinity. But though we had driven
them away, the pestilence seized on ourselves in strange and
marvellous fashion, for some lost their strength, and their legs
grew big and swollen, their sinews¹⁶ shrank and became black
as coal, and in some cases were spotted thick with purple
blotches of blood. Then the plague passed up into their
haunches, thighs, shoulders, arms, and neck. And in all cases
the mouth grew so foul and rotten about the gums, that the
flesh dropped off to the very roots of the teeth, nearly all of
which fell out. And this disease raged so in our three ships
that in mid-February, of our company of 110 men not ten were
whole, in so much that one could not aid another, which was
a pitiful sight to see considering the place wherein we were.
For the people of the country came every day before our
fort, and saw few men on their feet, and already eight were
dead, and more than fifty without hope of life. Our captain
seeing misery and sickness so general, ordered all to turn to
prayers and orisons,¹⁷ and ordered an image in the likeness of
the Virgin Mary to be carried across the snow and ice and
placed against a tree, a bow-shot from the fort, and gave
orders that on the following Sunday Mass should be said at
this spot, and that all, sick or well, who could walk should
go in procession singing the seven psalms of David, and the
Litany, and praying the Virgin to deign to implore her dear

15 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stadacona> Stadacona, a 16th-century Iroquoian village near Quebec City.

16 Sinew. Tendon, ligament.

17 Orison. Prayer.

Son to have pity on us.¹⁸ Mass said and sung before this image, the captain vowed himself a pilgrim to our Lady to whom prayers are said at Rocamadour [or rather *Roqu'amadou*, meaning the Lover's Rock. This is a town in Quercy much frequented by pilgrims], if God gave him grace to return to France. That day died Philippe Rougemont, a native of Amboise, aged about twenty years.

p.150

p.151

And for that the said sickness was unknown, our captain ordered the body to be opened to see if we could get any knowledge of it, to preserve if possible the rest of us. We found his heart all white and withered, and about it more than a quart of water as red as a date; the liver healthy, but the lungs black and gangrened, and all his blood drawn into a clot above his heart, for when he was opened, from above his heart sprang a great jet of foul, black blood. Further, his spleen toward the spine was somewhat mortified for about two inches, as though it had been rubbed on a rough stone. After seeing this we made an incision, and cut

18 The Protestant Hakluyt translates what follows: "praying most heartily that it would please the said our Christ to have compassion upon us." A line or two above he had changed the image of the Virgin into "in remembrance of Christ, caused his Image to be set upon a tree."

The Seven Psalms are the Penitential Psalms, *i.e.* vi., xxxii., xxxviii., li., cii., cxxx., cxliii., in the Protestant versions (vi., xxxi., xxxvii., l., ci., cxxix., cxlii., in the Vulgate); the Litany is the ordinary Litany of the *Processionale* in the Roman Breviary, frequently known as the "Litaniæ Sanctorum."

The combination of the Penitential Psalms and the Litany is an ordinary one; *e.g.* it is said on all Fridays in Lent in the present Roman use. It is the ordinary form of a special "rogation," and was thus the natural thing for Cartier to use under the circumstances. I owe this note to the Rev. F. E. Brightman of Magdalen College, Oxford.

Here and elsewhere the question arises, whether there were priests with Cartier on his voyages, (1) He several times speaks of Mass being heard or sung. (2) An incomplete list of his crew on the second voyage has been preserved, and includes Dom Guillaume Le Breton and Dom Anthoine, the title usually given to priests, and in Brittany in the sixteenth century especially applied to an unbeneficed priest or chaplain. (3) When the Indians asked Cartier what weather they would have on the way to Montreal, and whether he had spoken to Jesus on the subject, "il repondit que ses Pretres y avoient parlé" (see Chap, xiv.) On the other hand, on several occasions on which we would expect their presence, it is not mentioned; some of these are so striking that Dr. Dawson (*op. cit.*, pp. 185-187), while leaving the matter open, is inclined to decide in the negative. Thus at Hochelaga, "Cartier himself read the Gospel of St. John and the Story of the Passion out of his book of hours. He stroked the limbs of the paralytic chief and prayed for the conversion of the savages" (Dawson). Amid all the woes of the winter, they are never mentioned as "baptizing, comforting, exhorting, or burying." At Stadaconé, when Donnacona and several others asked for baptism, Cartier replied "That there was no one then who could teach them the faith," but that on another occasion "he would bring priests and chrism." (Lescarbot, book vi., chap, iv.) Belleforest (*Cosmographie Universelle*, ii. 2188) takes this as decisive evidence against their presence. While certainty is of course impossible, my own belief is that the frequent mention of the Mass outweighs the other evidence. The priests may not have gone to Hochelaga, but have remained behind on ship-board. Cartier's refusal of baptism is more difficult to explain, but it is possible that his priests were down with scurvy, in which case they were in a sense the proto-martyrs of the Canadian Church.

open his thigh, which was all black on the surface, but the inner flesh was sound enough. This done, he was buried in as seemly fashion as we could. God in His holy grace have mercy on his soul, and on all dead men. Amen.

And thereafter from day to day this sickness so spread that a time came when in our three ships there were not three sound men, so that in one of them there was not a man who could go below deck to draw drink either for himself or for the others. And at this time there were already many dead, whom in our weakness we were forced to bury under the snow, for it was impossible for us at that time to open the frozen ground, so weak were we, and so feeble our strength. And we were also in great dread lest the people of the country should perceive our misery and weakness. And to hide our illness, when they came near our fort, our captain, whom God preserved in continual health, went out to meet them with two or three men, well or ill, whom he made come out behind him. And when he saw them outside the pale, he made pretence of striking them, shouting and throwing sticks at them, sending them on board, making signs to the savages that he was keeping his men at work within the ship, some caulking,¹⁹ others baking, others at different tasks, and that it would not do for them to come loafing outside; this the savages believed. And our captain bade the sick men hammer and make a noise within the ships, beating with sticks and stones, pretending to caulk. And at that time so many were down with the disease that we had almost lost hope of ever returning to France, had not God in His infinite kindness and compassion looked on us in pity, and given us knowledge of a remedy against all maladies, the best that was ever seen or found on earth, as we shall now relate. But first you must know that from mid-November to the 18th²⁰ day of April, we were continuously shut in by the ice, which was more than two fathoms thick; and on the ground the snow was four feet in height and more than two fathoms thick;²¹ in so much that it was higher than the sides of our ships, and endured all that time; so that our drink froze fast in the casks, and high and low within the ships there was four inches of ice upon the wood; and the whole river was frozen as far up as the fresh water extends, above Hochelaga. In this time we lost to the number of twenty-five of the best and kindest sailors whom we had, who died of this disease; and there were more than forty of whom we had no hope, and save for three or four all the rest without exception were ill. But God, in His holy grace, looked on us in pity, and sent us a remedy for our health and healing of the kind and in the way that we shall now relate.

p.152

19 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Caulk>

20 Cartier says 15th; Hakluyt "until the midst of March."

21 The last six words are an error of the printer, whose eye was caught by the preceding line. They are not found in the edition of 1609.

One day our captain seeing the plague so rife and his men so greatly overcome by it, had gone out of the fort and was walking on the ice, when he saw approaching a band of the people of Stadaconê,²² and among them Domagaya, whom, ten or twelve days before, the captain had seen very ill of the same sickness as his men; for one of his legs was swollen to the size of the body of a two years' old child, and all its sinews were shrunk; his teeth were decayed or gone, his gums rotten and foul. The captain seeing him hale and whole, rejoiced greatly, hoping to find from him how he had been healed, in order so to give aid and help to his men. p.153

And when they had come near the fort, the captain asked him how he had cured himself of his disease; Domagaya replied that he had been cured by the juice of the leaves of a tree, and their dregs,²³ and that this was the only remedy for this disease. Then the captain asked if there were not some of it near at hand, and to point it out to him, to heal his servant who had caught the said disease in the house of the chief Donnacona, not wishing to let him know the number of his sick comrades. Then the said Domagaya sent two women with our captain in search of it, who brought back nine or ten boughs²⁴ and showed us that one must strip off the bark and leaves from the wood, and set the whole mass to boil in water, and then drink this water every second day and put the grounds on the sick and swollen limbs, and that this tree cured of all diseases. And in their tongue this tree is called Anneda.²⁵

Thereupon the captain ordered this brew to be made for the sick men to drink of, but not one wished to try it, save one or two who risked the experiment. Very soon after they had drunk of it they felt better, which was a true and evident miracle. For, after having drunk of it two or three times, p.154

22 Stadaconê is the village of the Canadians. [L.]

23 Dreg. The sediment of liquids.

24 Bough. A branch of a tree; especially a main branch.

25 Amedda (Cartier). Ameda or Hanneda (Hakluyt). "Some writers suppose this to have been the white spruce (*Picea alba*), and others the white pine (*Pinus strobus*); but the *P. alba* is the better anti-scorbutic" (Baxter). Professor Ganong thinks that the reference on the next page to its size points to the white pine, which is the largest tree of Eastern Canada. Dr. Dawson, *St. Lawrence Basin*, p. 174, identifies it with the balsam fir, *Abies balsamea*. The quickness of its operation is not unnaturally exaggerated by the grateful Cartier. On this Dr. Dawson says: "Cartier, with his usual good judgment, limits the miracle to the apparent accident of the way he obtained knowledge of the remedy by his meeting with Domagaya; but some late writers go further, and, forgetting that the pagan Indians partook of the benefit to an equal extent as the Frenchmen, imagine that the virtues of the tree were specially conferred and did not avail on subsequent occasions." I do not see why it is good judgment to admit the miraculous, but to restrict it to the smallest possible dimensions; the view that the whole cure was due to the interposition of providence, which is apparently that of Mr. Joseph Pope, *Jacques Cartier*, p. 101 (Ottawa, 1890), is certainly more consistent than that of Dr. Dawson.

Pope: Jacques Cartier:

<https://archive.org/details/jacquescartierhi00popeuoft/page/8/mode/2up>

https://archive.org/details/cihm_12076/page/n11/mode/2up

from every disease whereby they had been attacked they recovered health and healing; insomuch that some of the crew who had had the French pox²⁶ for five or six years were clean cured by this medicine. On seeing this all crowded round the said medicine, so that they were like to kill one another in their desire to be the first to take it; in so much that as large and tall a tree as ever I saw was used up in less than a week; which wrought so well that if all the doctors of Louvain and Montpellier had been there with all the drugs of Alexandria, they would not have done as much in a year as this tree did in a week. For it so profited us that all who were willing to make use of it recovered health and healing, thanks be to God.

26 French pox; the French disease.
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Syphilis>